

STUDENTS' READING PRACTICES AND COMPREHENSION IN URBAN AND RURAL SCHOOLS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 1

Pages: 13-24

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2438

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13876029

Manuscript Accepted: 08-26-2024

Students' Reading Practices and Comprehension in Urban and Rural Schools

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Abstract

Reading practices provide the bases by which students build their reading skills, particularly reading comprehension. This study aimed to look into the level of students' reading practices and their comprehension levels. This descriptive-correlational and comparative research was conducted at Pagadian City Science High School, Pagadian City as the urban school and Molave Vocational Technical School, Molave, Zamboanga del Sur as the rural school, during the school year 2018-2019. It utilized Grade 7 learners as research respondents. Findings revealed that students' reading practices in the urban school were high in terms of reading motivation and reading materials exposure but low in terms of social influence in reading. On the other hand, students' reading practices in the rural school were high in terms of reading motivation but low in terms of social influence in reading and reading materials exposure. In the urban school, 84% of the students fell in independent level, 16% fell in instructional level and no students fell in frustration level. In contrast, in the rural school, 64% of the students fell in independent level, 36% fell in instructional level and no students fell in frustration level. A significant difference existed between the reading practices of students in urban and rural schools and reading comprehension of students in urban and rural schools. A significant relationship existed between students' reading practices and their reading comprehension. These findings indicate that the students' reading practices are of great help in improving their reading comprehension. An appropriate action plan was proposed to improve the reading practices as well as the reading comprehension of the students in the rural school.

Keywords: *reading practices, reading comprehension, urban and rural schools*

Introduction

Reading is a crucial ability that serves as the basis for all types of learning and is a must for every subject taught in school (Sattar & Salehi, 2014). Students must analyze a text by identifying the constituent terms of each phrase in a paragraph and determining the precise meanings of each individual word. By understanding the combined meaning of these words, students may completely comprehend the text.

Basaraba et al. (2013) defines reading comprehension as an intricate cognitive process that necessitates the utilization of various foundational skills. This is a prevalent issue among contemporary pupils. Lions and Peña (2016) discovered that reading comprehension in numerous Latin American countries falls below the worldwide benchmark. Comparable findings have been noted regarding the reading comprehension abilities of students in the Philippines. Several educators' express dissatisfaction with pupils' lack of reading comprehension or their inability to comprehend written material, as noted by Miciano (2007). An observation frequently seen in reading lessons or English classes, particularly in government public high schools, is that students exhibit a lethargic and easily tired disposition towards reading. During a 2007 interview, Dr. Yolanda Quijano, the director of the DepEd's Bureau of Elementary Education, identified reading difficulties as the primary cause for the subpar academic achievement of certain kids in the NAT.

If a student's reading comprehension is deficient, it is likely that their performance in other areas will be impaired. During an interview with former Department of Education Secretary Br. Armin A. Luistro, he emphasized the significance of evaluating pupils' reading proficiency as it serves as the fundamental basis for all academic knowledge acquisition. He stated that if a student does not acquire fundamental reading abilities from the beginning, they will consistently face difficulties in succeeding in other subjects, so preventing them from being literate and productive individuals.

This issue can be resolved by employing various reading techniques or routines that students and teachers must employ. According to Foasberg's (2014) survey, the majority of rural students considered reading related to their courses to be extremely important, and they typically preferred reading in print format. They frequently practiced responsive reading while studying for their classes, using both printed and technological materials. Nevertheless, people typically opt for print materials when reading for their academic courses. In contrast, Morton's (2008) study found that children in urban schools exhibited favorable reading engagement with non-traditional books beyond the classroom. The majority of these pupils were exposed to beneficial reading practices by their family members, who read books to them during their youth.

Sadeghi (2007) distinguishes between internal and external factors as potential influences on reading comprehension. The internal factors are variables that are unique to the reader. This applies to all elements that are associated with the reader. Internal components may encompass cognitive capabilities, techniques, affective qualities, and background knowledge. On the other hand, external factors include text variables, context variables, and writer variables.

The internal elements influencing reading comprehension primarily revolve on the students. Consequently, pupils are provided with an activity to enhance their reading comprehension skills. In order to enhance their reading comprehension, individuals must engage

in self-development. In order to enhance their reading comprehension, it is imperative for them to employ appropriate reading techniques or routines. The study conducted by McGeown, Griffiths, and Stothard (2014) largely focuses on the relationship between reading motivation, reading habits, and reading skill. However, the majority of research in this area has mostly concentrated on using reading comprehension as the measure of reading outcomes.

The researcher has direct experience with the current reading comprehension challenges that are prevalent among high school students, particularly in the rural school where they are currently employed. Additionally, there is a dearth of prior research that has focused on the disparities in reading comprehension levels and practices between children in urban and rural institutions. Nevertheless, the correlation between reading comprehension and reading practices has been thoroughly investigated. The primary goal of this investigation is to establish a correlation between reading comprehension and reading practices. Furthermore, it endeavors to ascertain whether there are any discrepancies in the levels of reading comprehension and reading practices between rural and urban institutions. The primary goal is to establish a strategic approach that effectively addresses the persistent issue of inadequate reading comprehension among students, with a particular emphasis on the educational institution of the researcher.

Research Questions

The main goal of the investigation is to ascertain whether there is a correlation between the reading practices of the students and their reading comprehension. Particularly, the investigation sought responses to the subsequent inquiries:

1. What is the level of reading practices of students in urban and rural schools in terms of:
 - 1.1. reading motivation;
 - 1.2. social influence in reading; and
 - 1.3. reading material exposure?
2. What is the percentage of reading comprehension of students in urban and rural schools?
3. Is there significant difference in the reading practices among learners in urban and rural schools?
4. Is there a significant difference in reading comprehension between learners in urban and rural schools?
5. Is there a significant relationship between learners' reading and their reading comprehension?
6. Based on the results, what course of action can be designed to improve students' reading practices and reading comprehension in both urban and rural schools?

Literature Review

Reading Practices

Individuals engage in specific activities and behaviors when reading, which are referred to as reading practices. These are related to the process by which individuals generate reading experiences, engage in discussions about their reading, and derive significance from it. The process of reading is influenced by and contributes to the diverse ways in which individuals engage with reading, and it can be both social and individual (Barton & Hamilton, 2000). Reading behaviors are categorized into three sub variables in this study: reading motivation, social influence on reading, and exposure to reading materials. Subsequent paragraphs will address each of these.

Increasing the desire to read. Prior study has established the importance of all pupils developing their own consistent reading routines. There is a significant relationship between the amount and frequency of reading that youngsters do and their level of literacy success (Guthrie & Wigfield, 2001). Nonetheless, the 2005 NAEP and other study findings indicate that student engagement and achievement in reading have decreased (Perie & Moran, 2005). In addition, the findings of a study on the reading habits of sixth- and seventh-grade urban students were presented at a panel discussion at the 2006 NCTE Conference. The study discovered a contradictory situation in which pupils expressed a lack of interest in reading despite being confident in their reading ability.

Ivey and Broaddus (2001) validate the notion that in order for students to achieve a minimum level of proficiency in reading, it is imperative for them to consistently participate in reading activities. However, in order to engage in consistent reading, pupils must possess the drive to cultivate a curiosity for reading (Moje, 2006). Research has consistently shown that reading motivation is a reliable indicator of reading comprehension and proficiency (Hedges & Gable; Ahmadi, 2013).

Reading motivation is commonly understood to consist of two elements: inner motivation and extrinsic incentive (Ahmadi, 2013). Intrinsic motivation is characterized by action that is motivated by internal incentives. For example, learners are more likely to engage in extensive reading if they possess a genuine interest in the subject matter and are given the freedom to select their own reading materials. Extrinsic motivation, in contrast, is associated with the incentive that an individual will receive as a consequence of an action. Typically, grades serve as the primary external motivators for reading habits (Hairul et al, 2012). Research by Houghton (2015) indicates that intrinsic desire is a more accurate indicator of high success in reading. Takaloo and Ahmadi (2017) found that students typically choose to read for entertainment, selecting materials that are humorous, enjoyable, or otherwise appealing to them.

A number of experts strongly support the idea of allowing students to choose their own reading materials during class as a means of fostering enthusiasm for reading. However, it might be difficult to cultivate a genuine excitement for reading among students due to their fleeting and short-lived interest in particular titles and themes (Mercurio, 2005). An additional approach to comprehending

students' reading preferences is to examine the literate activities in which students partake outside of the educational setting (Hughes-Hassell & Rodge, 2007).

The effect of social variables on reading. Reading practices are the ways that students use to derive meaning from the act of reading and writing texts, drawing on their social and cultural ideas, cognitive processes, and goals. The term 'cultural' in this sense refers to the various effects influenced by one's household, community, colleagues, and contemporary cultural trends. Students draw meaning and acquire understandings, principles, and perspectives on the use of reading by making a link between the words in a text and their own personal experiences. According to Hughes-Hassell and Rodge (2007), students' future reading habits might be influenced by reading activities outside of the classroom. The impact of social practices on learning and understanding argues that humans' high cognitive capacities are influenced by interactions in their immediate environment (Bruner, 1990; Vygotsky, 1986). As a result, students' reading habits are inextricably related to their interactions with family, friends, and the school setting. Students' social and cultural experiences have a substantial impact on their reading habits, preferences, and understanding. Furthermore, these encounters are critical in determining what knowledge and insights students gain from their reading. Galvez (2004) analyzed the level of assistance provided to rural high school pupils with their reading activities at home. The study found a substantial association between children's cognitive abilities and the aid they receive at home. As a result, students at the given university are more likely to use home reading aid as part of their reading routine. This is congruent with Vygotsky's theory, which holds that children gain mastery or expertise in a highly valued activity in their community (Vygotsky, 1986). According to researchers, kids who build reading habits outside of school might make links between their personal reading habits and academic reading, resulting in academic literacy competency (Alvermann, 2004).

Malette (2005) described social literacy studies as a broader concept of literacy. It addresses the idea that reading and learning in the classroom should involve socially engaged groups that collaborate to make sense of content from a range of sources, both within and outside of school. It has extended to encompass social literacy, such as discussing rap songs, TV shows, movies, and magazine articles.

According to Barton and Hamilton (2000), social literacy is the participation of local communities in literacy-related activities in order to entertain themselves and form social links with others. As students and teachers come from varied social and cultural backgrounds, it is critical to understand the social literacy activities that urban and rural children engage in outside of school. Teachers can enrich students' academic reading experiences by recognizing their social context and the different knowledge they have accumulated, allowing them to provide transforming experiences. Social literacy research investigates the impact of familial, peer, and media interactions on students' self-perceived reading abilities, which are influenced by their attitudes, values, and beliefs. Early reading experiences with families play an important part in shaping children's reading identities. As a result, the setting in which a student finds themselves has a significant impact on information intake, comprehension, and application. According to Whitmore and Norton-Meier (2008), how families believe and behave about reading has a long-term impact on children as they grow into teenagers. In addition, their peers' reading habits and attitudes play an impact.

Morton's (2008) study discovered that students in urban schools had higher levels of reading engagement with non-traditional literature outside of the classroom context. The majority of these students were introduced to good reading habits by their parents, who read them books when they were little.

During the latter years of elementary and middle school, peers' values and beliefs begin to have a more substantial impact on the lives of teenagers than their family's influence (Urduan & Midgley, 2003).

Exposure to reading materials. Several studies have looked into the differences in reading habits between students in urban and rural areas, specifically in terms of access and exposure to reading materials. According to Gao (2017), pupils who live in urban areas are more likely to come from affluent families and privileged communities, giving them more opportunity to access educational resources. Furthermore, Cartwright and Allen (2002) observed that students in rural locations are less likely to have a computer or internet access at home than their urban counterparts. Lone (2011) also emphasized that rural populations may experience a relative scarcity of sufficient knowledge and resources, such as public libraries and internet access. In addition, Nawe (2016) emphasizes that the reading materials offered in urban school libraries are of higher quality and more recent. As a result, rural pupils have fewer opportunities for reading. This has a huge impact on their reading engagement, since Mboacha (2015) observed that many readers in rural areas avoid reading due to a lack of available materials. Adolescents in both urban and rural schools appreciate a wide variety of genres, according to reading preference data. These include specialist periodicals, comic books, novels based on cartoons, movies, and TV shows, magazines, instructional texts, horror stories, book series, picture books, and poetry (Greenberg et al., 2006; Ivey & Broaddus, 2001). Morton et al. (2008) found that seventh-grade kids in metropolitan regions read at a higher level, particularly with periodicals, newspapers, and online publications. During a two-year ethnographic study of a sixth-grade Language Arts class, students were observed picking nonfiction books for recreational reading based on personal interest, personal connections, or visual beauty (Moss & Hendershot, 2002).

Reading Comprehension of Students

Reading comprehension is the primary goal of reading since it extracts meaning from written material. It would be incorrect to characterize the passage as reading if infants speak words without understanding their meaning. Reading comprehension is a complete

process that involves combining the reader's prior knowledge with the information delivered in the text to infer meaning from written material (Imam, 2016). To develop meaning, pupils must interact successfully with the text. They must use their knowledge to improve their understanding of the subject topic. Furthermore, comprehension is the process of extracting meaning from traditional written materials such as books, magazines, and papers, as well as listening to others read or watching a range of media formats that are widely available in the modern era (Miller, 2016). The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory Manual (2018) focuses assessing students' understanding levels, which are classed as Independent, Instructional, and Frustration. The ability of a youngster to read independently is referred to as "independent level." To determine the independent level, the test administrator gives a text one level lower than the current option until the kid achieves word reading accuracy of 97 to 100% and comprehension accuracy of 80 to 100%. To assess the child's ability in a given genre of literature, it is necessary to determine the independent level. Providing content at the autonomous level might serve as a foundation for training or a source of inspiration. The instructional level describes a child's capacity to read under the supervision of a teacher. This is the stage at which students make the most progress in their literacy skills. To determine the instructional level, the test administrator selects a passage that is somewhat more difficult than the learner's autonomous level on several occasions. This practice will continue until the student gets a comprehension accuracy of 59-79% and a word reading accuracy of 90-96%. (The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory Manual is provided below, 2018, p. 11).

The frustration level is the point at which an infant becomes unable to read and comprehend independently. The test administrator continually gives the student with passages that are one level more difficult than their teaching level in order to determine the depth of discontent. This method continues until the student's oral reading score in Comprehension and Word Reading falls below 58% and 89%, respectively. To determine the type of information for which the learner is not yet prepared, it is necessary to assess the level of dissatisfaction.

Local academics conducted a study on the reading comprehension abilities of students at remote universities. Ramirez's (2014) study found that children in both urban and rural schools in Margosatubig District, Division of Zamboanga del Sur, had lower reading comprehension than expected. The average percentage score from the students' reading comprehension assessments was used to perform the study. Furthermore, the study discovered that there is no significant difference in reading comprehension between the two student groups. Ramis (2008) discovered that reading comprehension among children in rural institutions was satisfactory. Cabardo (2014) conducted research on high school pupils' reading skills. According to his study's findings, the majority of the children exhibited excellent levels of reading skill when reading silently, but their voice reading was only at an instructional level. Furthermore, when compared to females, males have significantly lower levels of reading skill in both silent and oral reading.

Banquicio (2014) presented the findings from her research on the reading comprehension abilities of students in two rural schools. The survey discovered that high school students' reading comprehension was at the instructional level, with an average score of 63.22 percent. In contrast, students at another high school in the same province had a reading comprehension rate of 21.1%, showing frustration.

Suarez (2015) argued that the major goal of reading is to gain understanding. High school pupils are required to have high reading comprehension abilities. High school students are expected to understand, investigate, mix, and evaluate large amounts of content. Many English teachers have observed that during reading courses, some students struggle to answer fundamental questions that require them to recognize and comprehend specific features provided in the text. Most of them were unable to draw conclusions from facts not directly stated in the text. Some people struggle to recall earlier knowledge that they can apply to improve their reading comprehension.

Flowers and Flowers (2008) investigated the topic of urban high school students in their high school-level study. The Flowers and Flowers (2008) study was a longitudinal inquiry that looked at 752 schools from the 2001-2002 academic year, including public, Catholic, and private institutions. Notably, forty percent of the schools were in urban school districts. This study looked at standardized reading test scores, as well as factors including home environment, gender, income, parental educational levels, and how students spend their time after school. The study's findings found a high relationship between reading achievement and family affluence, parental expectations of education, and the amount of time students spent on homework. Lindsey's (2010) study on children's reading achievement in an urban school district discovered that students in urban schools have a strong and favorable level of reading achievement, as measured by an analysis of their reading comprehension test scores. Additional reading exercises can help to improve and clarify one's comprehension. According to Pressley (2003), increasing vocabulary, engaging in extensive reading, and practicing critical reading are all effective ways to improve and hone an individual's comprehension skills for any type of literature.

To improve reading comprehension, students should make an effort to thoroughly acquire and comprehend the material they have read, thereby raising their level of comprehension and becoming skilled readers. Students should engage in additional reading assignments throughout class to improve their reading skills and comprehension abilities (Richa, 2014). Paying attention to important details and taking notes while reading will help you understand the book better. Murray (2010) stated that a child with a thorough understanding of multiple disciplines will have better reading skills than a child who does not.

In accordance with this approach, Lavilla (2017) emphasized the necessity of students engaging in extensive reading and being directed to books appropriate for their level. This allows youngsters to actively improve their reading skills, learn new vocabulary, and be exposed to a wide variety of topics.

The review of relevant literature found a scarcity of materials relating to the two variables. As a result, the investigation's goal is to assess students' reading comprehension skills and behaviors in a focused manner. Any outcome of the inquiry is expected to be immediately influenced and supported by the preceding assumptions, pertinent discoveries, concepts, and theories.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher employed a descriptive-correlational design to collect the required data and information for this investigation. This methodology was deemed suitable as it sought to investigate the reading habits of students and the relationship between their reading habits and their reading comprehension. Ortiz (2016) states that descriptive-correlation analysis is intended to demonstrate the relationship between two or more variables.

The study employed a comparative approach to examine the disparity in reading comprehension across children in urban and rural schools. Pentti (2017) elucidated that comparative research allows the researcher to discern and investigate the resemblances and disparities among selected phenomena or groupings. Comparative study examines various examples, methods, and geographically specified agreements that may be compared.

Respondents

The study utilized Grade 7 students in urban and rural school in Zamboanga del Sur.

Table 1. *Research participants*

No.	Schools	Grade 7 Students	
		<i>N</i>	<i>n</i>
1	Urban School (Science Curriculum)	135	50
2	Rural School (Science Curriculum)	120	50
Total		155	100

The researcher used the random sample technique to determine the number of participants in this experiment. According to Ortiz (2016), random sampling is the process of selecting a sample so that every individual in the defined population has an equal and independent chance of being chosen for the sample. This is the most effective way for collecting a sample that accurately represents the entire population. Furthermore, this includes forming the population, enumerating each member, and selecting individuals at random for the sample. A random sample is frequently obtained by using a table of random integers. Each pupil was assigned a separate number. The researcher chose a number from the table of random numbers and included the students assigned to that number in the sample.

Instrument

In order to assess reading habits, the researcher employed a revised version of a questionnaire on reading habits derived from Morton's (2008) study. The items from the previous questionnaire were kept, but they were rearranged to align with the three components of reading practices that are relevant to the current study: reading motivation, social influence in reading, and exposure to reading material.

The participants responded to the checklist by drawing on their personal experiences or reading practices. The respondents were asked to rate the frequency of each situation on a 4-point scale, ranging from "Always" to "Never". Therefore, a score of 4 indicates consistent practice, a score of 3 indicates frequent practice, a score of 2 indicates occasional practice, and a score of 1 indicates no practice. The data was processed using the average weighted mean. The data were analyzed based on the hypothetical mean range as follows: 1.00 - 1.75 = very low; 1.76 - 2.5 = low; 2.51 - 3.25 = high; and 3.26 - 4.00 = very high. The researcher employed a reading comprehension exam derived from the Proficiency in English a Worktext in English 7 to assess the reading comprehension skills of Grade 7 pupils in both urban and rural schools. The students perused a text and subsequently responded to the multiple-choice inquiries. The kids' reading comprehension level was calculated using the formula prescribed by the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory. This technique involves dividing the number of right responses by the total number of items in the exam, and then multiplying the resulting quotient by 100 (Phil-IRI, 2018). The scores were further analyzed utilizing the scale provided by the same source.

Procedure

Prior to beginning the actual data collection, the preliminary stage in the data collection technique was followed. The researcher acquired formal authorization and consent from the Superintendent of Schools for the Division of Zamboanga del Sur and the Pagadian City Division. Furthermore, the principals of Pagadian Science High School and Molave Vocational Technical School granted permission to perform the study in urban and rural schools, respectively. After getting consent, the researcher set aside two days to conduct the survey at schools located in both urban and rural areas. On the first day, the researcher gave the participants an informed consent statement to read and comprehend. The participants next signed the consent form, indicating their desire to participate in the study. On the second day, after obtaining all necessary authorizations, the researcher conducted the survey, giving the participants an introduction to the study. The participants in this study were chosen from intact groups in Grade 7. The administration of the reading practices questionnaire is complete. Participants were then given a time limit to complete the reading comprehension evaluation. The

researcher directly oversaw the events. Throughout the poll, participants asked a variety of questions, and the researcher responded appropriately. The survey was completed in one hour and fifteen minutes. After acquiring all of the data, the researcher compiled the participants' responses to reading habits and reading comprehension outcomes into a table. After collecting the participants' responses, the researcher, in partnership with a statistician, collated, evaluated, and explained the data.

Data Analysis

The statistical techniques employed in this study encompassed both descriptive and Inferential statistics. The mean and standard deviation were utilized to ascertain the status of the two variables under investigation, while inferential statistics were used to assess the study's null hypotheses. The Pearson coefficient of correlation was used to establish the significant relationship between students' reading habits and reading comprehension.

Furthermore, the Independent Samples T-Test was used to determine any differences in reading practices and comprehension across rural and urban schools. To verify the credibility and trustworthiness of the results, the data was processed on a computer using the Special Package for Social Science (SPSS) software, since modern statistical technology is increasingly being used in educational research.

Ethical Considerations

The following factors were considered during the research: Research participants were not exposed to any form of damage or negative consequences. The prioritization of study participants' dignity was upheld. Prior to the trial, the subjects provided their full consent. Initially, the researcher prioritized honesty as one of the key considerations. Provide accurate and objective information regarding data, results, techniques, procedures, and the current state of publishing. Stringent measures were implemented to prevent the creation, distortion, or misinterpretation of data. Furthermore, the factor of integrity was also given careful consideration. The researcher upheld their pledges and agreements, demonstrated sincerity, and pursued consistency in their thoughts and actions.

Furthermore, the aspect of confidentiality was considered. The data collected from this research was handled with utmost confidentiality to prevent any potential harm to the participants. The researcher maintained the preservation of the research respondents' anonymity. Finally, any form of deceit or overstatement of the goals and purposes of the research was carefully prevented. Avoidance of any form of misleading information or biased representation of priority was ensured.

Results and Discussion

Students' Reading Practices

Students employ various methods and mediums to actively participate in the act of reading. They engage in various activities while reading. Within the context of this study, the term "reading practices" pertains to the specific actions and behaviors individuals engage in when they read. This study examined the process by which participants create reading experiences, discuss their reading, and derive meaning from it (Hamilton, 2000).

Level of Students' Reading Practices. The data on the results of the questionnaire checklist about reading practices in terms of reading motivation, social influence in reading and material exposure both in urban and rural schools were shown in the following tables.

Table 2 shows the level of students' reading practices in terms of reading motivation in urban and rural schools. As reflected in the table below, the urban school got an over-all mean of 2.92, interpreted as high, while the rural school got an over-all mean of 2.46, interpreted as low. This result showed that the Grade 7 students in the urban school are more motivated to read compared to those in the rural school.

Table 2. *Level of students' reading practices in terms of reading motivation*

Items	Urban School			Rural School		
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I love to read books.	2.86	0.73	High	2.82	0.80	High
2. After school, I go to internet cafes for reading.	2.44	0.81	Low	1.64	0.75	Very Low
3. At home, I read books for fun.	3.02	0.80	High	2.56	0.76	High
4. I do reading homework when it is assigned.	3.26	0.72	Very High	2.62	0.88	High
5. If I want to know information about something, I would look it up on a book.	3.00	0.86	High	2.66	0.82	High
Over-all Mean	2.92	0.78	High	2.46	0.80	Low

Note: 1.00-1.75, Very Low; 1.76-2.50, Low; 2.51-3.25, High; 3.26-4.00, Very High

According to the findings of Morton (2008), interest is the crucial factor in motivating the reader to deeply engage in the text and try to understand it better. Interest is an important motivator for the use of those strategies that enable deeper processing. It is significantly connected also with the other motivational factors, as for example involvement, enjoyment and persistence, which is reflected in the comprehension of text.

The table above shows that items number 1 and 3 are rated as high for both urban and rural schools, suggesting that intrinsic motivation

is high among the learners for both schools. This may influence their reading comprehension, as Houghton (2015) pointed out that intrinsic motivation tends to be a better predictor of good reading performance. Takaloo and Ahmadi (2017) similarly pointed out that students read more for fun and enjoyment than for study purposes. However, it must also be noted that items number 4 and 5 are also rated as high (or very high in the case of item number 4 for the urban school). Both items pertain to extrinsic motivation.

This table above also shows that for item number 2 “After school I go to internet cafes for reading” the urban school obtained a mean of 1.64, which is interpreted as low, while the rural school obtained a mean of 2.44, which is interpreted as very low. According to Morton (2008), students are reluctant to visit internet cafes for reading due to the inconvenience of distance from their homes and the necessity to return home promptly after class. Rural students are disproportionately affected by this, as they typically have limited access to computers or the internet at home, which in turn reduces their reading frequency (Cartwright and Allen, 2002).

Table 3 shows the level of students’ reading practices in terms of social influence in reading. Shown in the table below, the over-all mean of students’ reading practices in urban school is 2.50 and in rural school is 2.46. Both results were interpreted as low. This demonstrates that students’ engagement in reading was not influenced by their social influences.

Table 3. *Level of students’ reading practices in terms of social influence in reading*

Items	Urban School			Rural School		
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Someone in my family reads books to me.	1.86	0.76	Low	2.36	1.03	Low
2. I talk to my family about things I read.	2.66	0.87	High	2.56	0.91	High
3. I talk to my friends about things I read.	2.94	0.91	High	2.66	0.85	High
4. Adults in my home read magazines.	2.60	0.78	High	2.46	1.11	Low
5. In class, I like to talk about the similarities between my life and stories we read.	2.46	0.84	Low	2.26	0.72	Low
Over-all Mean	2.50	0.83	Low	2.46	0.92	Low

Note: 1.00-1.75, Very Low; 1.76-2.50, Low; 2.51-3.25, High; 3.26-4.00, Very High

The data also shows that both Items 2 and 3 were scored highly in both urban and rural schools; however, children in the urban school evaluated Item 4 with a mean of 2.60, implying that adults in their homes read their periodicals. This confirmed Morton's (2008) discovery that parents in urban student families read publications on a regular basis. As children grow into teens, their family attitudes and practices toward reading continue to influence them, as do their peers' reading experiences and perspectives (Whitmore & Norton-Meier, 2008). According to Alvermann (2004), students who adopt out-of-school reading practices may connect their personal reading practices to classroom reading and develop expertise in academic literacies, but they rarely communicate what they have read.

Table 4 depicts the level of student practice in terms of reading material exposure. The overall mean of pupils' reading material exposure in urban schools is 2.59, which is viewed as high, but in rural schools it is 2.09, interpreted as low. This indicates that students in urban schools have greater exposure to the resources indicated in the questionnaire than students in rural schools.

Table 4. *Level of students’ reading practices in terms of reading materials exposure*

Items	Urban School			Rural School		
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I read magazines.	2.00	0.73	Low	1.48	0.61	Very Low
2. I read newspapers.	2.06	0.74	Low	1.28	0.45	Very Low
3. I read journal articles.	2.72	0.86	High	2.22	0.68	Low
4. I read novels/fiction books.	3.38	0.85	Very High	2.60	0.88	High
5. I read nonfiction books.	2.78	0.89	High	2.86	0.93	High
Over-all Mean	2.59	0.81	High	2.09	0.71	Low

Note: 1.00-1.75, Very Low; 1.76-2.50, Low; 2.51-3.25, High; 3.26-4.00, Very High

This supports the findings of Gao (2017), Lone (2011), and Nawe (2016), who attributed the difference in exposure to reading materials in urban and rural areas to a number of factors: first, students from urban areas are more likely to be from wealthier families and more well-off areas, and thus more likely to have greater access to educational materials (Gao, 2017); second, rural areas tend to have a comparative lack of adequate information and sources (like This has an additional impact on the frequency with which pupils read, as many rural readers do not read due to a lack of preferred reading materials (Mboacha, 2015).

The table further shows that students in urban and rural school rated item 4 with mean of 3.38 and 2.60, respectively and the results were interpreted as very high and high and item 5 with a mean of 2.78 and 2.86, respectively which interpreted as high. This indicates that they are more exposed to fiction and non-fiction materials. This finding supports Morton's (2008) research, which discovered that mysteries, horror/ghost stories, adventure, boy/girl relationships, comics, realistic teenage fiction, science fiction/fantasy, and urban stories were the most popular genres among both urban and rural pupils.

The findings above support prior research on the formative role of print exposure in reading development (Mol & Bus, 2011). Furthermore, the observed findings support a broader view of print exposure as promoting the development of cognitive and scholastic skills other than reading, such as wide language functioning and syllogistic reasoning (Osana et al. 2007).

Summary Data on Students' Reading Practices. Table 5 shows the summary table of the students' reading practices in terms of reading motivation, social influence in reading and reading material exposure in urban and rural schools.

In terms of reading motivation, the students in the urban and rural schools obtained a mean of 2.92 and 2.46, respectively, interpreted as high. In terms of students' reading practices on social influence in reading, students in the urban and rural schools gained a mean of 2.50 and 2.46, respectively, both interpreted as low. In reading practices in terms of reading material exposure, it is clear that students in the urban school were more exposed to reading materials than in the rural school, since their mean is 2.59 and this is high compared to that of the rural school, which has only 2.09, interpreted as low.

The table below further explains that among the three indicators in reading practices, the urban school gained an over-all mean of 2.67, which is high, while the rural school gained an over-all mean of 2.34, which is low. This means that in the students in the urban school are more engaged in reading practices compared to those in the rural school.

Table 5. *Summary of students' reading practices*

Items	Urban School			Rural School		
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Reading Motivation	2.92	0.78	High	2.46	0.80	High
2. Social Influence in Reading	2.50	0.83	Low	2.46	0.92	Low
3. Reading Materials Exposure	2.59	0.81	High	2.09	0.71	Low
Over-all Mean	2.67	0.81	High	2.34	0.81	Low

In terms of social influence in reading, both urban and rural schools earned obtained a low interpretation from their mean percentage score. This may be because of some other factors that arise in their reading practices.

Students' Reading Comprehension

Students' reading comprehension is the result of the students' score in reading comprehension test. The level of students' reading comprehension was shown in Table 6. As shown in the table, in urban school, 42 out of 50 students or 84% were at the independent level, 8 or 16% were at the instructional level and no students were at the frustration level of reading comprehension. On the other hand, in rural school, 32 out of 50 students or 64% were at the independent level, 18 or 36% were at the instructional level and no students were at the frustration level of reading comprehension.

Table 6. *Level of students' reading comprehension*

Reading Level	Urban School		Rural School	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Independent Level (80% - 100%)	42	84%	32	64%
Instructional Level (59% - 79%)	8	16%	18	36%
Frustration Level (0% - 58%)	0	0%	0	0%
Overall	50	100%	50	100%

*N = 50

Testing the Hypotheses

Testing Difference in Reading Practices. The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in reading practices between students in urban and rural schools was tested using independent samples t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

By employing independent samples t-test, Table 7 shows that there is a significant difference in students' reading practices between the urban and rural schools. The table (t-value = 3.056; p-value = 0.003) reveals that students in the urban school have significantly higher level of reading practices than students in the rural school. Therefore, the first null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 7. *Independent t-test on students' reading practices in urban and rural schools*

Variables	Mean	SD	t-value	df	p-value	Remarks
Reading Practices in Urban School	2.67	0.43	3.056	72	0.003	Significant
Reading Practices in Rural School	2.34	0.22				

* Significant at the 0.05 level *(N=50)

Morton (2008) argued that children in urban schools showed positive reading engagement with non-traditional literature outside of class. The majority of these students had family members who modeled healthy reading behaviors and read books to them as children.

Testing Difference in Reading Comprehension. The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in reading comprehension between students in urban and rural schools was tested using independent samples t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

By employing independent samples t-test, Table 8 shows that there is a significant difference in students' reading comprehension between students in urban and rural school. The table (t-value = 2.180; p-value = 0.032) reveals that the students in the urban school

have a significantly higher level of reading comprehension than the students in the rural school. Thus, the second null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 8. *Independent t-test on students' reading comprehension in urban and rural schools*

Variables	Mean	SD	t – value	df	p – value	Remarks
Reading Comprehension in Urban School	17.34	1.80	2.180	97	0.032	Significant
Reading Comprehension in Rural School	16.50	2.04				

* Significant at the 0.05 level *(N=50)

In the study of Lindsey (2010) about the students' reading achievement in an urban school district, it was revealed that students in urban school show a positive and a high level of reading achievement as analyzed with the use of their reading comprehension test. The results of study discovered that reading achievement was positively affected by parental income, parental expectations of the student (for education) and the amount of time students spent on homework.

Testing Correlation of Reading Practices and Reading Comprehension. The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between students' reading practices in rural and urban schools and their reading comprehension was tested using Pearson Correlation test at 0.01 level of significance.

Table 9. *Test of relationship between reading practices and reading comprehension*

Variables	Pearson "r"	Interpretation	p-value	Interpretation
Reading Practices and Reading Comprehension	.379**	Weak Positive Linear Relationship	.000	With Significant Relationship

Note: 0 – ± 0.29 = No Linear Relationship; ± 0.30 – ± 0.49 = Weak Linear Relationship; ± 0.50 – ± 0.69 = Moderate Linear Relationship; ± 0.70 – ± 0.99 = Strong Linear Relationship; ± 1 = Perfect Linear Relationship; *N = 50; **Significant at .01 level

The findings revealed a slight positive linear association between students' reading practices and reading comprehension (Pearson "r" = .379), implying that the more students' reading practices are improved and developed, the better their reading comprehension. On the other hand, if such reading activities are inadequate, the likelihood of poor reading comprehension increases. Furthermore, a significant correlation was found between the two variables (p-value <.01). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis, stating that there is a strong association between students' reading practices and reading comprehension, was accepted. Reading practices are the ways in which students employ their social and cultural ideas, reasoning, and intentions to extract meaning from reading and writing texts. In this context, 'cultural' refers to influences from home, community, peers, and popular culture. By relating words in a text to their own experiences, children construct meaning and form attitudes, beliefs, and opinions about how reading is utilized. Student participation in reading practices outside of school has the potential to influence reading comprehension (Rodge, 2007).

Since a strong relationship has been demonstrated between students' reading practices and students' reading comprehension, it is recommended that both students and teachers work together to enhance students' reading practices in order to maximize reading comprehension.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study highlights the significant differences between urban and rural students' reading practices and comprehension levels. Urban students exhibited higher reading motivation and greater exposure to reading materials, which correlated with better reading comprehension. In contrast, rural students showed lower engagement in these areas, impacting their comprehension abilities. Both urban and rural students demonstrated limited social influence in reading, underscoring the importance of home and community support. The findings suggest that improving reading motivation and providing better access to reading materials are critical for enhancing comprehension, especially in rural schools. The study further established a weak but significant positive correlation between reading practices and comprehension. These results emphasize the need for targeted interventions to address disparities and support students' overall literacy development, particularly in under-resourced rural areas.

References

- Ahmadi, M. R. (2013). The relationship between reading motivation and reading comprehension. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(18).
- Alvermann, D. E. (2004). What could professional wrestling and school literacy practices possibly have in common? *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 47(4), 532-540.
- Baier, R. (2005). Reading comprehension and reading strategies. University of Wisconsin Stout.
- Banquicio, J. (2014). Home reading resources, contextual clues competence and reading comprehension skills. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Saint Columban College, Pagadian, City.
- Barton, D., & Hamilton, M. (2000). Literacy practices. In M. H. D. Barton, & R. Ivanic (Ed.), *Situated literacies: Reading and*

writing in context, (pp. 7-15). New York: Routledge.

Basaraba, D., Yovanoff, P., Alonzo, J., & Tindal, G. (2013). Examining the structure of reading comprehension: do literal, inferential, and evaluative comprehension truly exist? *Read Writ*, 26: 349-379. DOI 10.1007/s11145-012-9372-9

Block, C. C., & Pressley, M. (2007). Best practices in teaching comprehension. In L. B. Gambrell, L. N. Morrow, & M. Pressley (Eds.). *Best practices in literacy instruction* (3rd ed., pp. 220–242). New York: Guilford Press.

Bruner, J. S. (1990). *Acts of Meaning*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Cabardo, J. (2014). Reading proficiency level of students: basis for reading intervention program. Available at: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=2712237>.

Cartwright, F. & Allen, M. K. (2002). Understanding the rural-urban reading gap. *Education, Skills and Learning Research Papers*. Ottawa, Canada: Statistics Canada.

Flowers, L. (2007). Recommendations for research to improve reading achievement for African American students. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 42(3), 424-428.

Flowers, T., & Flowers, L. (2008). Factors affecting urban African American high school students' achievement in reading. *Urban Education*, 43(2). 154-171.

Flowerday, T., & Schraw, G. (2004). The role of choice and interest in reader engagement. *The Journal of Experimental Education*, 72(2), 93-114.

Foasberg, N. (2014). Students' reading practices in print and electronic media. *Journal of College and Research Libraries*, 13, 705-723. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5860/crl.75.5.705>.

Galvez, L.M. (2004). Home reading support, students' oral reading and reading comprehension competencies. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Saint Columban College, Pagadian City.

Gao, Q., Shi, Y., Yi, H., Abbey, C. & Rozelle, S. (2017). Reading achievement in China's rural primary schools: A study of three provinces. *Rural Education Action Program Working Paper 325*. Stanford University.

Greenberg, G., Rodrigo, V., Berry, A., Brinck, T., & Joseph, H. (2006). Implementation of an extensive reading program with adult learners. *Adult Basic Education*, 16, 81–97.

Guthrie, J., & Wigfield, A. (2001). Engagement and motivation in reading. In M. L. Kamil, P.B. Mosenthal, P.D. Pearson, & R. Barr (Ed.), *Handbook of reading research: Volume 3* (Vol. 3). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.

Hairul, N. I., Ahmadi, M. R., & Pourhossein, A. G. (2012). The role of reciprocal teaching strategy as an important factor of improving reading motivation. *Elixir educational technology*, 53(3).

Hedges, J. L., Gable, R. (2014) The relationship of reading motivation and self-efficacy to reading achievement. Trumbull, CT: Northeastern Educational Research Association.

Houghton, K. L. (2015). Impacts of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on reading achievement of first-grade students. Walden University.

Hughes-Hassell, S., & Rodge, P. (2007). The leisure reading habits of urban adolescents. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 51(1), 22-33.

Imam, O. (2016). Effects of Reading Skills on Students' Performance in Science and Mathematics in Public and Private Secondary Schools. *Journal of Education and Learning*. Vol. 10 (2) pp. 177-186.

Ivey, G., & Broaddus, K. (2001). "Just plain reading": A survey of what makes students want to read in middle school classrooms. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 36(4), 350-377.

Kumar, R. (2011). *Research methodology: A step by step guide for beginners* (3rd edition). London, UK: SAGE Publications.

Lavilla, M. (2017). Students' reading skills and comprehension levels. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Saint Columban College, Pagadian, City.

Lindsey, K. (2010). Reading achievement in an urban school district (Order No. 3438579). Available from ProQuest Central. (848434831). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/848434831?accountid=141440>.

Lions, S. & Peña, M. (2016). Reading comprehension in Latin America: Difficulties and possible interventions. *Child and adolescent development in Latin America. New Directions for Child and Adolescent Development*, 152, 71–84. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cad.20158>.

- Lone, F. A. (2011). Reading habits of rural and urban college students in the 21st century. *Library Philosophy and Practice Paper No. 586*. Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/586>.
- Malette, M. (2005). What matters most? A survey of accomplished middle-level educators' beliefs and values about literacy. *Action in Teacher Education*, 27(2), 33-42.
- Mboacha, E. (2015). A comparative study of the reading comprehension of English second language learners between urban and rural schools in Limpopo province. Unpublished Mini-Dissertation. University of Limpopo, Limpopo, SA.
- Mcgeown, S. P., Duncan, L. G., Griffiths, Y. M., & Stothard, S. E. (2015). Exploring the relationship between adolescent's reading skills, reading motivation and reading habits. *Reading and Writing*, 28(4), 545-569. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11145-014-9537-9>.
- Mercurio, M. (2005). In their own words: A study of suburban middle school students using a self-selection reading program. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 49(2), 130-141.
- Miciano, R. (2007). Two reading problems of Filipino students. Manila.
- Miller, C. (2006). What is comprehension? Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/paqsw>.
- Moje, E. (2006). Motivating texts, motivating contexts, motivating adolescents: An Examination of the role of motivation in adolescent literacy practices and development. *Perspectives, the Journal of the International Dyslexia Association*, 34(3), 10-14.
- Mol, S. & Bus, A. (2011). To read or not to read: A meta-analysis of print exposure from infancy to early adulthood. *Psychological Bulletin*, 137, 267–296.
- Morton, S. (2008). At-risk, urban seventh and eighth grade summer school students' perspectives on their reading practices and preferences Available from ProQuest Central. (304369472). Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/304369472?accountid=141440>.
- Moss, B., & Hendershot, J. (2002). Exploring sixth graders' selection of nonfiction trade books. *The ReadingTeacher*, 56, 6–17.
- Murray, A. (2010). High school subjects for self-study, volume 1. 1611, Quezon Avenue, Quezon City: Success Unlimited Enterprises.
- Nawe, B. L. (2016). The reading habits among library users in rural and urban areas of Sarawak, Malaysia. *The International Academic Forum*.
- Ortiz, C. (2016). *Fundamentals of Methods of Research*. Malaybalay, Bukidnon: CKU Digital Supplies and Services.
- Osana, H. et. al. (2007). The impact of print exposure quality and inference construction on syllogistic reasoning. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 99, 888–902.
- Pardede, P. (2008). A review on reading theories and its implication to the teaching of reading. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321228081>.
- Perie, M., & Moran, R. (2005). The nation's report card; NAEP 2004 trends in academic progress: Three decades of student performance in reading and mathematics. (NCES-464): U.S. Department of Education; Institute of Educational Sciences.
- Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (2016).
- Ramirez, H. (2014). Language experience approach, pupils' oral reading competence and reading comprehension skills. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Saint Columban College, Pagadian City.
- Ramis, J. (2008). Teaching word-learning strategies, vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension skills. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Saint Columban College, Pagadian, City.
- Richa, C. (2014). Reading attitude, reading enhancement skills and reading comprehension. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Saint Columban College, Pagadian, City.
- Rumelhart, D. (1980). Schemata: The building blocks of cognition. In Spiro, R., Bruce, B. and Brewer, F. (Eds.) *Theoretical Issues in Reading Comprehension*. Hillsdale, NJ.
- Sadeghi, K. (2007). "The key for successful reader-writer interaction; factors affecting reading comprehension in L2 Revisited" *Asian EFL journal*, 9 (3), article 10. http://www.asian-efl-journal.com/sept_2007_ks.php. Retrieved July 12, 2018.
- Suarez, G. (2015). The reading comprehension of students. Definitely Filipino. <https://definitelyfilipino.com/blog/reading-comprehension-of-students>.
- Takaloo, N. M., Ahmadi, M. R. (2017). The effect of learners' motivation on their reading comprehension skill: A literature review. *International Journal of Research in English Education*, DOI: 10.18869/acadpub.ijree.2.3.10.

Urdan, T. C. & Midgley, C. (2003). Changes in the perceived classroom goal structure and pattern of adaptive learning during early adolescence. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 28, 524-551

Vygotsky, L. S. (1986). *Thought and language*. A. Kozulin (Ed.), Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press.

Whitmore, K., & Norton-Meier, L. (2008). Pearl and Rhonda: Revaluating mothers' literate lives to imagine new relationships between homes and elementary schools. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 57(8), 450-461.

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